

TRIBOLOGICAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MICROWAVE PROCESSED KENAF/HDPE COMPOSITES UNDER DRY SLIDING WEAR

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Introduction

- Now-a-days, green polymer composites have attracted more attention in different manufacturing sectors such as automotive, packaging industries, and construction industries.
- Natural fibres are good substitutes for polymeric composites owing to various advantages such as renewable nature resources, low weight, cost, density and easily available.
- In present research work kenaf (20 wt.)/HDPE composites were fabricated using microwave assisted compression moulding.
- The tribological behaviour of microwave processed kenaf/HDPE composites were assessed using a pin-on-disc tribometer.
- Sliding speed and normal load was varied in the range of 1-3 m/s and 10-30 N, respectively.
- The effect of the sliding speed and normal load was observed on the coefficient of friction and specific wear rate.
- Hardness test was also carried out as per ASTM D2240.

Materials and methods

Fig. 1: Schematic of different stages during dry sliding wear

Results and discussion

Fig. 2: SEM images of composite at sliding velocity (a) 1 m/s (b) 2 m/s (c) 3 m/s and at normal load of 20 N

Fig. 3: Effect of normal load on friction force at different velocity

Fig. 4: Effect of normal load on friction coefficient

Fig. 5: SWR vs sliding distance at different velocity

Fig. 6: Effect of normal load on specific wear rate

Fig. 7: Effect of sliding velocity on SWR

Fig. 8: Hardness of specimens

Conclusions

- Microwave assisted compression moulding seems to be good to fabricate NFRPCs.
- Reinforcing kenaf fibre enhanced the wear property of the NFRPCs.
- There was increment of 70% in frictional load as the normal load increases from 10 N to 30 N.
- Specific wear rate (SWR) increases as the sliding distance, sliding velocity and normal load increases.
- Hardness of the NFRPCs was increased by 5.2% on adding the 20 wt.% kenaf fibre into neat HDPE.